

Initial Demonstration of an X-Band Digital Beamforming (DBF) Receive Array

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Abstract—This paper^{1,2} presents the architecture and initial measured performance of an X-Band Digital Beamforming (DBF) Plug-and-Play Receive Array. This processor was designed to steer four independent simultaneous beams over the entire X-band with 32 independent channels, an instantaneous bandwidth of 15 MHz, and a spur-free dynamic range of at least 65 dB. Designed using commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) components, we achieved a vast decrease in size of the DBF processor. When compared to previous DBF systems, the system's ease in mobility and measurement accuracy greatly increases DBF's applicability towards smaller airborne platforms.

Using AFRL-SNHA's in house facilities, we have begun to measure and test the Plug-and-Play processor's current capabilities. These measured capabilities include not only the ability to form multi-beam, uniformly illuminated broadside and scanned array patterns, but also its ability to reduce the array sidelobes, using tapered illuminations. Measurements to date have been taken using only 8 to 12 channels, but work is currently underway to utilize the processor's full capacity. However, these initial measurements and results demonstrate that this DBF processor exhibits exceptional array processing capabilities, while possessing an overall small system footprint.

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1. INTRODUCTION

DBF is an advanced approach for steering phased array antennas. The analog techniques previously developed for the electronic steering of phased arrays relied on components such as line stretchers, phase shifters, time delay lines, and attenuators. DBF reduces the need for these components by digitizing the received signals. Beam steering in DBF systems can simply be achieved using signal processing techniques in the digital domain. Another advantage of digitizing the (RF) energies include the ability to produce multiple and adaptive beams with greater ease than conventional analog phased arrays. Unfortunately, due to the size, weight, and power constraints of current and past systems, DBF's airborne applications have been few. By building upon past in-house DBF systems [1], some of which took up 36 cubic feet of space and weighed over two hundred pounds, the goal of this project was to produce a custom DBF system with state of the art capabilities, while reducing the system size and weight. Using COTS components to design this system, the Plug-and-Play receiver was able to be encased in a 20"x19"x4" sized box, weighing less than twenty-five pounds.

Designed and developed by Applied Radar, Inc., the Plug-and-Play system integrated two individual hardware designs [2]. The first section, the X-band digital receiver, consists of the RF down converter circuitry as well as the data acquisition module (DAM), which converts the analog RF energy into a digital format. The second component of the hardware architecture, the DBF processor, was designed to generate four, real-time, simultaneous beams using data streams from the thirty-two individual receivers.

To understand how the Plug-and-Play system operates and performs, it is first important to become acquainted with the theoretical assumptions and calculations used for its design. These parameters assisted in developing the receiver architecture as different components and their limitations were considered. This design process has been previously

documented in past publications [2], [3]. Integration of these individual components leads directly to the frequency response of each channel and thus also helps derive the processor's calibration scheme to enable accurate array processing. The final step in developing this system was to design and construct a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that controlled the total experimental system, producing the measured results which will be shown below.

2. SIGNAL PROCESSING

The Plug-and-Play processor and each digital receiver module were designed to have 15 MHz of instantaneous bandwidth, a bandwidth which allows us to classify the incoming signals as narrow band when considering the system was designed for use at X-band. The narrow-band assumption lets us avoid time-delay processing and simplifies both the receiver's and the processor board's design. Current analog-to-digital (A/D) technology, with increased sampling speeds and larger word lengths, also played a key role in the implementation of all the signal processing computed by the processor.

Using RF cables, signals from each element are transferred from the antenna to the digital receivers. The first basic step of the receiver is to down convert the received signal to an intermediate frequency (IF) at which we sample. Using the narrow band assumption for the received signal, the DAM was designed to bandpass-sample a signal of bandwidth 15 MHz centered at the IF of 75 MHz. Since the sampling frequency is 60 MHz, much less than the Nyquist sampling rate for the IF, the sampled signal will be aliased [4] down to a center frequency of 15 MHz. However, by sampling the original signal at 60 MHz, the message signal is still adequately sampled and can be properly reconstructed [5]. This sampling frequency not only satisfies the Nyquist criterion, but also aids further to ease the signal processing, which will be shown later in this section.

At this point in the design, the desired message signal is in a digitized format with a carrier frequency of 15 MHz. To perform beamforming, we must now extract the I and Q signal components. The DAM uses digital decomposition in order to achieve this step. There are two main advantages to separating the signal components digitally at the IF: (1) concerns of gain balancing for I and Q channels are eliminated, and (2) analog DC offsets and drifts do not occur in the I/Q demodulator [6]. Although this process produces some quadrature detection error, for narrowband systems this error is considered to be at insignificant levels [6]. If we wished to eliminate this error altogether, Hilbert transforms could be used to implement the digital decomposition. However, the ease at which the digital demodulation can be performed far outweighs the computational requirements for the finite impulse response (FIR) filters required to implement a Hilbert Transform.

To perform the I and Q decomposition, the input data stream is digitally copied and each stream then individually multiplied by either a cosine or sine waveform. For the Plug-and-Play processor, the cosine and sine waveforms are implemented using the respective, repeated multiplier coefficient strings $\{1, 0, -1, 0\}$ and $\{0, 1, 0, -1\}$. One copy of the data stream is multiplied using the first set of multiplier coefficients for successive data samples while the other data stream is multiplied by the second set of coefficients. At the global system clock rate of 60 MHz, these series of multiplier coefficients are equivalent to cosine and sine waves of one-fourth the clock rate, 15 MHz. Figure 1 below helps to illustrate this process.

Figure 1 – Sampled Sinusoidal Waves

Figure 1 shows an analog cosine and sine wave, each at a frequency of 15 MHz. Also along the plots are the waveforms' discrete representations sampled at 60 MHz. As can be seen from Figure 1, these discrete representations are given by the repeated strings $\{1,0,-1,0\}$ for the cosine wave and $\{0,-1,0,1\}$ for the sine wave, thus visually demonstrating how the DAM creates the mixing waveforms for I and Q decomposition. By multiplying the aliased IF data by these waveforms, the output is not only just the I and Q components of the signal, but the data streams have also now been mixed down to baseband.

Now the message signal is at baseband with little or no distortion, since the mixing process does not affect the bandwidth of the I and Q signal components. At the output of the digital mixer, both of the signals are baseband limited to 7.5 MHz while the signals are still sampled at 60 MHz. From the Nyquist theorem, it can be seen that the I and Q components are over-sampled and can therefore be down-sampled, or decimated, by a factor of two and still sufficiently represent the analog signals. This reduces the data flow throughout the processor and therefore also reduces the system's computation load in future processes.

3. PROCESSOR ARCHITECTURE AND DATA FLOW

The digital receivers and the DBF processor utilize FPGAs in their hardware architecture. Due to the FPGA's large number of input/output (I/O) pins and embedded multipliers, the use of these configurable chips allows for both a high data throughput and high computational rate. These are important design considerations due to the word length of the A/D converter (14 bits) and the number of simultaneous beams the processor is designed to compute (4). The reasons for this will be discussed in more detail further below.

Each digital receiver contains one FPGA devoted to the processing of a single channel. The I and Q signal components from each module are then outputted in separate streams at 30 MHz to the DBF processor board. The DBF processor has a total of nine FPGAs, eight for receiving and implementing the complex weighting (CMULT)³ of the data from the DAM modules and one other (TCOP)³ used to interface between the PC and all other FPGAs. The eight CMULTs are devoted to receiving, weighting, and outputting the digital data streams from four separate DAMs. Once data is received by the CMULT, it is digitally copied into four separate bins and weighted to produce four simultaneous beams. Data for each beam is then combined into a partial beam sum for continued summation with the weighted data from all other CMULTs. All partial beam sums are combined using a pipelined architecture where the output of the final CMULT is a complete beam sum. After the final CMULT, the beam data is then transferred to a SDRAM module where it is held until a command from the PC to extract the data.

Both the CMULTs and DAMs possess registers which contain the beam weights necessary for beamforming. The registers in the DAMs constitute a 10-tap FIR filter, which can be implemented for equalization of the channel across the system bandwidth as well as for tapering the antenna pattern. The CMULT coefficients are used to weight the input data to form each of the four beams. Through these weights, we create the equivalent of phase shifts required for beamforming in an analog phased array system.

The TCOP is the interface between the PC and all the FPGAs in the processor and receivers. Through the TCOP, every component register is read from and written to. The TCOP also acts as the interface between the PC and the SDRAM that holds the pipelined beam data from the CMULTs until a request is made from the PC.

Data word length, I/O pins, number of beams, and method of data transfer are all important aspects of this architecture. Because each CMULT accepts four, 28-bit wide data

³ We will use these acronyms when distinguishing between the different functionalities of the separate FPGAs. Their meanings are unimportant for our discussion, but understanding that two separate chips' functionalities work together on the processor board is a key concept in understanding the functionality of the DBF processor board.

streams from its specified digital receivers, the CMULT requires 112 I/O pins for just data input. Considering this and the number of additional pins required for output, control, and synchronization signals between chips, the total I/O pin count begins to increase rapidly. Fortunately, the complexities of the communication between components, as well as the number of I/O pins required to transfer data, coupled strongly with the advantages and capabilities of the FPGA.

4. DIGITAL RECEIVER FREQUENCY RESPONSE

The digital receiver module, shown in Figure 2, is the combination of a RF down-converter and a DAM. Each receiver is approximately 2.4"x2.4"x1.2" and weighs about 7 ounces. This small weight and size enables the total weight contribution from all 32 receivers to be less than 13 pounds when the DBF processor board is fully populated. When compared to off-the-shelf DBF systems, which may require multiple VME cards stacked into a high-speed data bus backplane to achieve the same number of channels, our DBF system requires much less space.

Figure 2 – Digital Receiver

Since the receiver module is the initial active component of the overall receive chain, it is important that the receiver itself demonstrates a fairly constant magnitude response across the system bandwidth. In order to do this, however, its individual components also need to exhibit a constant frequency response.

The RF down-converter, shown in Figure 3, is a single-stage design. The gain of this component was tested across the bandwidth of the system. Figure 4 shows that the down-converter exhibited a fairly constant magnitude response across the X-band frequencies with a gain variation of less than 12 dB.

Figure 3 - RF Down Converter Block Diagram

Figure 4 - Magnitude Response of RF-Down-Coverter

Integrating the RF down-converter with the DAM results in a digital receiver with a frequency response as shown below in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Magnitude Response of Digital Receiver

As shown in the figure, while the RF signal is swept across the system's instantaneous bandwidth of 15 MHz, the magnitude response stays fairly consistent with an absolute deviation of less than 3 dB. Using this relatively flat frequency response, the array calibration process will be simplified greatly.

5. CALIBRATION

Calibration between channels for any beamforming system is a critical requirement for accurate performance. Phase and magnitude variation between channels can occur easily due to the short wavelength of X-band frequencies combined with small variations in the physical travel path of the analog signal before digitization. To illustrate this importance, both a calibrated and uncalibrated pattern are shown below in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Calibrated and Uncalibrated Array Patterns

As is shown in the figure, the uncalibrated measurement displays sidelobe degradation and shallower nulls. This figure demonstrates that accurate calibration will be an important factor in the measurement accuracy.

One advantage of DBF systems is the ease in which they can be calibrated. If we assume the sampling of all signals occurs at the exact same moment for every channel, the only magnitude and phase errors we need to account for in narrowband systems are those that occur from the analog components before digitization. These components include the antenna elements, transmission lines, and the RF down-converters. What makes the calibration so simple is that these errors accumulate as the signals propagate through the channels, and, since the system is narrowband, the errors can be removed by using only one magnitude and phase correction in the digital domain.

To calibrate the DBF Processor, our system first records each channel's frequency response. The processor then selects the channel with the smallest magnitude response and designates that channel as the reference. For all channels, magnitude ratios are computed between the response of the reference and each individual channel. The magnitude ratios will be applied to the signals in order for the array to be uniformly illuminated. The phase response of each channel is also calibrated using similar means. While calculating the magnitude ratios, the processor also calculates the phase differences between the reference and each individual channels. These phase differences can then be applied to the calibration weights in order to achieve a

uniform phase front across all the channels. The magnitude ratios and phase differences are combined into complex-valued error correction weights and individually applied to each channel for calibration. The two Figures 7 and 8 below show the accuracy of the calibration, which in most cases showed a maximum difference of 0.1 db in magnitude and a maximum phase error of 1 degree.

Figure 7 - Magnitude Calibration Plot

Figure 8 - Phase Calibration Plot

It should be noted that the calibration process selected the channel with the smallest magnitude response due to the firmware and software. At the time the calibration process was coded, the software did not yet have the functionality to amplify signals for calibration so selecting the weakest signal and attenuating the other channels seemed appropriate. If desired, more recent implementations of the experimental software can use the channel with the largest response for calibration.

6. GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE (GUI) DESIGN

Our desire to configure different experiments rapidly, led us to develop the GUI for the DBF processor which resides on a host PC connected to the DBF processor. Controlling different types of equipment, each of which has its separate

control software, is the goal of the interface. We used Visual Basic as our development tool because of its user friendly environment, user friendly control of all development controls, user friendly linking between PC and equipment, and its extensive libraries for controlling equipment.

The first step in developing the GUI, shown below in Figure 9, was gaining computer control of the DBF receiver, antenna mount controller, and two signal generators. Since the DBF processor is a custom system, no control software existed. Extensive work was performed by Applied Radar to develop hooks in its firmware for communicating between the PC and all of the components on the processor board through a USB2.0 connection. These libraries were in DLL format and could simply be added to the GUI library for use in the source code. Controlling the antenna mount controller and signal generators was straight-forward, since they conformed to the NI 488.2 standards for outside communication to a PC.

Figure 9 - GUI Interface

The next step in development was to tailor the control software for the different types of functions required for the measurements. The main functions were broken into three broad categories and include calibration, applying complex weights, and collecting antenna patterns.

Each of these broad functions played a key role in the development of our measured results. For ease of the experimental process, weighting for both calibration and beamforming was required to be automated and scalable for up to 32 elements. This enabled the array to be reconfigurable for improved validation as measurements began to use a larger number of channels. For efficiency, the measurement process was also automated. Producing measurements required the control of two separate systems, the antenna mount and the DBF processor. Coordination between the mount and the processor allowed data to be recorded at specified angles as the antenna mount was rotated. It is with these three basic functions that all measurements shown in this paper were generated.

7. MEASURED VERSUS PREDICTED

PERFORMANCE

Predicted Performance

The predicted performance was computed using standard equations for estimating a phased array's far field pattern [7]. As we will show, predictions based on these equations along with an appropriate model for the element patterns from the antenna array, corresponded well to the measured results.

Phased-Array Antenna

A photo of the phased array used for the measurements is shown in Figure 10. The array consists of a flared parallel plate waveguide using SMA probe connectors for its 70 elements. It measures approximately 48" wide and 9" deep.

Figure 10 - Angled View of Antenna

The element spacing is uniform across the array with a distance of 0.65", equivalent to half-wavelength spacing at a carrier frequency of 9 GHz. Initial tests showed the antenna elements had a strong magnitude response at 9.5 GHz, so all measurements were taken using this frequency. The initial array measurements consisted of only the 12 center elements in the array; all other elements were terminated using matched loads, so any edge effects could be assumed immeasurable.

Phased-array simulations shown in textbooks often assume that the individual element patterns model a $\cos^{3/2}$ pattern. From the $\cos^{3/2}$ pattern, we are able to derive other characteristics about the expected array pattern, such as the beamwidths and sidelobe levels at given scan angles. Unfortunately, the element pattern from the array in Figure 10 differs from this standard.

Figure 11 – Measured, and $\cos^{3/2}$ Element Patterns

Due to the horn geometry [8], dimensions of the array, mutual coupling, and other electromagnetic effects, the measured element pattern exhibits different behavior when compared to the standard theoretical $\cos^{3/2}$ pattern above in Figure 11. Notice that the peak gain occurs at scan angles of about -60 and 60 degrees, while the gain at broadside is about 5 dB lower than the peak maximum gain. This will cause our measured array patterns to look different than an array pattern simulated with a standard cosine element pattern. From this point on, array patterns shown will take this measured element pattern into account.

Measurement Setup

All measurements were performed at AFRL-SNHA using the experimental platform seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Experimental Setup

This Figure shows the phased array (1), DBF receiver (2), LO source and distribution (3), as well as the necessary power supplies (4) mounted onto an antenna mount. The mount is located on the inside of a blind covered with RF absorber to reduce reflections from the antenna mount and surrounding equipment, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 – Experiment Viewed Setup from 36°

Across from the experimental setup in Figure 13, reside a transmit horn and RF source, which are used to transmit the input RF waveforms to the DBF system. From the DBF processor, data flows to a host PC located directly to the rear of the antenna mount, also hidden by the blind. All array measurements were taken by setting the digital weights to electronically scan the array in a desired direction, and then physically rotating the antenna mount 180° and recording a measurement for every increment of 1 degree the mount moved.

Broadside Patterns with Uniform Illumination

Some of the first patterns attempted with the Plug-and-Play receiver were taken using twelve elements at broadside. This is shown below in Figure 14. As with all antenna patterns given from here to the end of the paper, Figure 14 is normalized to the directivity at the desired scan angle. Figure 14 demonstrates how well the measured pattern corresponds to the simulated pattern. Note that the location of the peaks and nulls, especially within 45 degrees from broadside overlay each other almost exactly. Also note that the sidelobe levels are much higher than an array pattern using a cosine^(3/2) element pattern as in Figure 11, especially at the outer scan angles. To visualize why this occurs, Figure 14 also includes the measured element pattern to display where the element's peak gains occur in reference to the elevated sidelobe levels of the array patterns. Taking into account the array's element pattern, we are able to show how well the DBF processor performs for a broadside scan angle.

Figure 14 - Measured and Predicted Broadside Patterns

Scanned Patterns with Uniform Illumination

Figures 15, 16, and 17 show the measured results for array patterns scanned to 20, 35, and 55 degrees, respectively, where it can be seen that the peaks and nulls of the measured and predicted patterns are in close agreement. A strong point of interest is how well the main beams of the predicted and measured patterns correspond. Even at the farther scanned angles (55 degrees for these plots), the main beam's shape matches the shape of the predicted beam with great accuracy.

Element patterns are included in Figures 15-17 to show why the sidelobe levels are considerably higher at the more extreme scan angles than if the element exhibited a cosine^(3/2) pattern. One example of this effect is shown in Figure 15, where it can be seen that the sidelobes adjacent to the main beam differ from each other in magnitude. This can help to be explained by observing the difference in gain of the element pattern at the location of the sidelobes' peaks, which also vary in a similar manner.

Figure 15 -Array Patterns Scanned 20 Degrees

Figure 16 - Array Patterns Scanned 35 Degrees

Figure 17 - Array Patterns Scanned 55 Degrees

Patterns with Sidelobe Control

In order to take advantage of a phased array's ability to produce extremely low sidelobe patterns, the DAMs were equipped with FIR filters to implement element tapering and channel equalization. Although these registers are able to provide additional array processing capabilities, for our initial measurements we elected to implement sidelobe tapers by adjusting the magnitudes of the complex beam weights. By using the CMULT registers, we were then able to implement patterns using sampled Taylor distributions [7] [8] that reduce the sidelobes to lower levels as compared to an uniformly illuminated array.

The initial measurements using Taylor Line Synthesis are unable to present a clear picture about the accuracy and performance of the DBF processor due to fact that only array patterns using eight elements have been measured using Taylor Synthesis. This provides little insight as to how the processor will perform since an eight element array only has 3 sidelobes on each side of the main beam to manipulate, but nevertheless, these patterns do show

promise to the accuracy at which the sidelobe levels can be reduced.

Figures 18 and 19 below show two cases as to how well the DBF processor can execute a small Taylor taper. Figure 18 demonstrates the differences between the predicted and measured Taylor tapered array pattern with -15 dB sidelobes and where n is 2. The sidelobes adjacent to the main beam are a bit higher than predicted, but at larger scan angles the measured and predicted patterns begin to align.

Figure 18 - Broadside Taylor Pattern (-15 dB, $n=2$)

Similar to Figure 18, higher, adjacent sidelobes, when compared to the predicted pattern, can also be observed in Figure 19 below. Figure 19 demonstrates the differences in the predicted and measured Taylor tapered array patterns with -20 dB sidelobes and $n=2$.

Figure 19 - Broadside Taylor Pattern (-20 dB, $n=2$)

Again, the sidelobe peaks adjacent to the main beam are higher than predicted, but when compared to Figure 18, we can see that they have been lowered by 2 to 4 dB. This decrease is not quite the 5 dB expected, but it provides encouragement for further research in sidelobe reduction and inherent system errors.

When scanning a tapered array, the measured result is similar to those measured in the two previous figures at broadside. Figure 20 below is a Taylor tapered array pattern with -15 dB sidelobe levels and $n=2$ scanned to 10 degrees.

Figure 20 - Scanned Taylor Pattern (-15 dB, $n=2$)

Once again, the sidelobes adjacent to the main beam have peak levels that are a bit higher than the model predicts. However, notice the beam peaks and nulls of all other lobes, including the main beam, match fairly well to the simulated model. This gives an indication that as the array size is increased and we are able to properly pick optimal numbers for the sidelobe levels and n , the DBF processor should perform with agreement in respect to the predicted models.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Using COTS components, we have designed, constructed, and tested a custom DBF processor. This system, when compared to previous and current systems, shows a large reduction in factors pertaining to size, weight, and power. The initial performance of the DBF processor has also been shown to be promising. Measurements demonstrating the processor's ability to calibrate, take broadside, scanned, and tapered array patterns has been shown to agree with the predicted models. The one limitation at the time of print was the number of elements the processor was capable of handling. This problem, however, is not design-related and it will be alleviated shortly by modifying the DBF processor software so it can handle all 32 channels.

Further work is currently being performed with this processor. Patterns with larger number of elements are being measured to continue to test scan and sidelobe reduction limits. Since the patterns presented are only initial measurements, an exhaustive effort should be performed to understand the systematic errors inherent to the processor. If the system continues to behave similar to the predictions, this technology could be applied to smaller platforms, both airborne and ground-based, where DBF had previously been unattractive due to its size, cost, and weight.

Furthermore, a new generation of the Plug-and-Play processor is being developed. This new processor will be able to provide both transmit and receive functionality, a stronger, more robust chassis, and the ability to generate its own LO for RF down and up-conversion, making the processor an almost stand-alone device.

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BIOGRAPHY

Daniel N. Spendley received the B.S. degree in electrical engineering from the University of Colorado at Boulder in 2003, and is currently pursuing the M.S. degree at Harvard University in Cambridge, MA. During the summer of 2002, he interned with the Naval Research Laboratory's Radar Division designing digital hardware for radar systems. He has been with the Air Force Research Laboratory's Antenna Technology Branch since

2003 designing and working with digital beamforming systems. Daniel is also a member of IEEE, Tau Beta Pi, and Eta Kappa Nu.

Lt Joseph D. Rosal received the B.S.E.E. degree from the University of Florida in 2003. Upon graduating cum laude, he received a commission into the Air Force from the ROTC program. His first assignment brought him to the Air Force Research Laboratory, Hanscom AFB, MA where his work has focused on digital beamforming technologies.

David D. Curtis is the Technical Advisor of the Antenna Technology Branch, AFRL/SNHA, of Air Force Research Laboratory, Sensors Directorate, Hanscom AFB, MA. He also serves as co-leader for the Apertures Subthrust, within the Sensors Directorate's RF Thrust. After joining Rome Air Development Center, in 1986, he performed research and development in a wide range of advanced phased array technology, including digital beamforming (DBF), photonic beamforming, phased array radiation performance, and digital array architectures. He has worked on a variety of phased array applications for advanced airborne radars, space-based radars, satellite communications and ground-based arrays before entering research engineering management five years ago. David received the BSEE and MSEE degrees from Northeastern University in Boston, MA, in 1986 and 1989, respectively, and is a member of IEEE, Tau Beta Pi, and Eta Kappa Nu.

Dr. William H. Weedon is president and founder of Applied Radar Inc. based in North Kingstown, RI USA (www.appliedradar.com). He received the BSEE (1989) and MSEE (1990) from Northeastern University, Boston, MA and the PhD in Electrical Engineering (1994) from the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. Dr. Weedon has published a number of technical articles, filed several patent applications, and has served as principal investigator on numerous contract research and development projects involving radar and electronics systems for the US Department of Defense. He is active in the IEEE, serving as the Antennas and Propagation Society Boston Section co-chairman in 2002 and 2003, helped coordinate the IEEE phased-array

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John J Burroughs received his B.S. degree at Roger Williams University in May, 1991. He is a Senior Embedded Hardware/Software Engineer. He has over fifteen years of Hardware and Embedded Software Design experience. He was with Motorola for 17 years where he designed Hardware and Software for networking products. After that he spent 5 years with Helix Technology designing Hardware and Embedded Software for Cryogenic Vacuum Control Products. Just before joining Applied Radar, John was designing Embedded Software on a complex video processing module based on a Power PC.

